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**SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC PREDICTORS OF UTILISATION OF MATERNAL
HEALTHCARE SERVICES AMONG WOMEN IN YENAGOA LOCAL GOVERNMENT
AREA OF BAYELSA STATE**

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Abstract

Studies have shown that there is low level of maternal health care utilization among women of childbearing age. The aim of the study is to investigate the socio-demographic predictors of utilization of maternal health care service among women of child bearing age in Yenagoa local government area of Bayelsa State. A descriptive research design was used for the study. A sample size of 500 was drawn from five hospitals using systematic random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was structured questionnaire with a 0.91. Data collected were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.0. Frequency, percentage, correlation and chi-square statistics were used. The result of the study showed that there was a high relationship between utilization of maternal health care services and socio-demographic variables such as age ($r = 0.82$), educational level ($r = 0.80$), marital status ($r = 0.84$), income ($r = 0.78$) and parity ($r = 0.79$). However, only educational status ($p < 0.05$), marital status ($p < 0.05$) and income ($p < 0.05$) were found to have statistically significant relationship with the utilization of maternal health care services. Thus, it was concluded that the socio-demographic predictors of utilization of maternal health care services among women in Yenegoa are educational status, marital status and income level. It was recommended among others that comprehensive health education on orthodox maternal healthcare practices should be emphasized during antenatal, postnatal visit, in the media and community meetings.